

Bank Sinarmas Sharia And Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around Bank Sinarmas Sharia and Conventional. The research was conducted from 2010 to 2022, by searching national journals indexed by Sinta via the Garuda website, with the keyword "Bank Sinarmas". Based on the search results, there were 50 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a Library Research study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every time years. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to Bank Sinarmas is divided into 9 clusters and 94 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a Library Research study, there are 5 play themes related to Bank Sinarmas Sharia and Conventional.

Keywords: Bank Sinarmas Sharia and Conventional; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research

Introduction

Banks are an industry whose activities depend on public trust. Banks are considered a place that customers trust to manage their funds (Harnani & Ng, 2019). In Indonesia, there are two types of banks, namely conventional banks and sharia banks (OJK, 2017). Conventional banks earn rewards in the form of interest while Islamic banks operate based on Islamic principles Which No allow exists usury or flower, but use principle for results. Moment This, there is Lots bank in Indonesia, Good bank conventional and Islamic banks. One of them is Bank Sinarmas. Bank Sinarmas is a conventional bank which also has a sharia business unit called Bank Sinarmas Syariah. Second bank the own superiority each. Wrong One superiority which are owned Bank Sinarmas is his abilities print profit as big as Rp 127.74 billion in 2021, or 8% from the previous year (Anggraeni, 2022).

In previous research, Bank Sinarmas has various information system applications that are used to support business operations and provide better services to customers. Several examples of information system applications used in Sinarmas Bank between others: Core Banking Systems, Internet Banking, Mobile Banking, ATM, Customer Relationship Management (CRM), Risk Management System, and Business Intelligence (BI) (Labibah and Fakhruddin, 2017; Nurfauzan and Faizatunnisa, 2021). Apart from that, there is an application for calculating customer points at Bank Sinarmas based on a loyalty program called Sinar Reward. This program makes it possible customers Bank Sinarmas For gather points with carry out certain transactions with their credit or debit cards, and then exchange those points for various rewards such as electronic goods, plane tickets, or shopping discounts at certain stores. To collect points, customers must make transactions with a Bank Sinarmas credit or debit card. Each transaction made will provide different points depending on the type of transaction and nominal purchase. The larger the nominal purchase, the more points the customer will get. To find out the number of points that have been collected,

customers can see them in their credit or debit card transaction report (Prasetyo, 2021).

There is very little scientific research on Bank Sinarmas Syariah. Based on search via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba), there are only 2 research that discusses financial performance analysis and the role of competency empowerment on employee work performance. Meanwhile, for conventional Bank Sinarmas, based on searches on the same website, there were 48 studies. This shows that research on Bank Sinarmas needs to be studied further. Research on Bank Sinarmas Syariah and conventional can currently be said to be quite small compared to research on other banks. This research is different from previous studies. The aim of this research is to determine the development of Bank Sinarmas Syariah and conventional from 2010 to 2021 using the VOSviewer bibliometric method and Library Research.

Literature Review

PT Bank Sinarmas Sharia Tbk is Wrong One bank sharia in Indonesia which operates with principles sharia Islam. Bank This established on year 2002 and headquartered in Jakarta. Bank Sinarmas Syariah offers various sharia financial products and services, such as sharia savings, sharia deposits, sharia financing, And card credit sharia. Besides That, bank This Also give service sharia consulting and investment to help customers manage their finances more effectively. Bank Sinarmas Syariah is committed to providing the best service while still upholding sharia principles. This bank also continues to strive to develop product and service innovations that suit the needs and desires of its customers (Banksinarmas, 2018).

Bibliometrics is branch of science who analyzes and evaluate scientific publications and related information. It involves the use of statistical and informatics methodologies to assess the production, citation, and dissemination of knowledge in the literature scientific. Studies bibliometrics can used For measure performance And individual contribution, institution, And field knowledge, as well as For understand interaction And connection between fields of science And publication. This Also can help in identification And evaluation trends and issues in scientific literature. Some applications of bibliometric studies include network analysis citation, analysis clusters, And analysis visibility. Results from studies bibliometrics can be used by researchers, government, and industry to understand developments and contributions in the field of science and to determine future research directions (Dubyna et al., 2022).

VOSViewer is bibliometric software used for visualization and analysis of scientific publication data. It allows users to visualize citation, co-citation, and co-word analysis data in the form of intuitive graphs and diagrams And easy accepted. VOSviewer can help researcher And analyst in conducting citation network analysis, finding relationships between scientific fields, and understanding trends and issues in scientific literature. It also helps in determining future research directions and gaining insight into the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions, and scientific fields. VOSviewer has an easy-to-use user interface and can be used in conjunction with data coming from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. It allows users to visualize and analyze publication data effectively and efficiently (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Library Research study is a process that includes identification, evaluation, and synthesis of results from previous research on a specific topic. It aims to provide an overview of trends, issues, and advances in related fields and assist in understanding how previous research influences future research

developments and directions. Library Research studies are usually conducted as part of the research process to ensure that researchers understand the existing research environment and produce non-duplicative results. This Also help in determine problem And gap in literature existing and assists in the formulation of hypotheses and understanding of specific research areas. Library Research studies can be carried out by accessing scientific publication databases, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Researchers can also carry out manual searches through scientific journals and related books. Library Research studies must be carried out with a systematic and objective methodology to ensure that the results are accurate and valid (El-Halaby et al., 2021).

Methodology

Study This use method study with approach mix-method, ie method quantitative on studies bibliometrics And method qualitative on studies Library Research. The research object is Bank Sinarmas Syariah and Conventional. Data type Which used is data secondary. Room scope data Which used is a scientific publication article about Bank Sinarmas originating from a national and accredited journal. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then searching for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Bank Sinarmas " throughout the year (2010-2022); (2) collect data title journal in Microsoft Excel, And identify title double journal; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on Library Research studies (Budianto, 2022).

Results And Discussion

Mapping Spread Publication Scientific About Bank Sinarmas Sharia and Conventional

The results of searching scientific publications about Bank Sinarmas Syariah and Conventional from 2010 to 2022 show fluctuations from year to year, especially in the five last year. In the year of 2019, number of publications most of them

published were 13 articles. On average, there are around 3 or more scientific publication articles about Bank Sinarmas Syariah and Conventional each year.

Table 1. Data publication scientific around Bank Sinarmas Sharia And Conventional by year

Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication
2010	1	2016	2	2020	6
2012	1	2017	7	2021	4
2013	2	2018	3	2022	6
2015	3	2019	13	2023	2
Amount 50					

Source: Data processed, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 2 show affiliate or institution Which most Lots publish articles study about Bank Sinarmas Sharia And Conventional. Journal Public Administration and EMBA Journal: Economic, Management, Business and Accounting Research Journal is the journal publishing institution that publishes the most research results on Bank Sinarmas Sharia and Conventional, with a total of 2 articles.

Table 2. Affiliate/institution publisher journal around Bank Sinarmas Sharia and Conventional

Name Affiliates/Institutions	Amount Publication
Journal of Public Administration., EMBA Journal: Journal of Economic, Management, Business and Accounting Research	2

Economic Dynamics - Journal of Economics and Business.,
 Infotek: Journal of Informatics and Technology., JBMI
 (Journal of Business, Management and Informatics)., Jesya
 (Journal of Economics and Sharia Economics)., JIM UPB
 (Scientific Journal of Management, Putera Batam
 University)., JMM Unram- Master Of Management Journal.,
 JMMS - Mandiri Saburai Management Journal., Journal Of
 Applied Finance & Accounting., Journal the Winners:
 Economics, Business, Management, and Information
 Systems Journal., Jurakunman (Journal of Accounting and
 Management)., Muhammadiyah University Accounting
 Journal Kupang., Journal Appreciation Economy., Journal
 Business and Economics., Journal of Economic Review.,
 Journal of Effective Economics., EMBA Journal: Journal of
 Research in Economics, Management, Business and
 Accounting., FEB Student Scientific Journal., Scientific
 Journal of MEA (Management, Economics, & Accounting).,
 Journal of Science Finance and Banking (IF) Undiksha
 Citizenship., Journal of Education, Psychology and Health
 Research (J-P3K)., Semarak Journal., Sisfotek Journal
 Global., Management & Business Journal., Pulpit
 Education., MONETARY - Journal of Accounting and
 Finance., MUST: Journal of Mathematics Education,
 Science and Technology., Medical Nexus Community.,
 Socio e-Cons., VISIONIST., Widya
 Management.

1

Source: Data processed, Microsoft Excel 2016.

The next table shows that the most productive researchers are Areros, Dwi Budi, Putra, Srisulistiowati, and Trisnowati, who each wrote 2 articles.

Table 3. Productivity researcher around Bank Sinarmas Sharia And Conventional

Researcher	Amount Publicati on
Areros, Bi Budi, Son, Srisulistiowati, Trisnowati	2

Achmad Irvan Dwi, Afriana, Ahmad Mukhlis, Aisyah, Amelya Augusthina, Anak Agung Dwi Widyani, Angga Harman, Anis, Ardiansah, Ash-Shiddiq, Ayu, Ayusari, Baiq Ariska Candra, Budi, Burhanudin, Corry, Dewa Made, Elisabet Tambunan, Esterina, Eugenia Hendrini P, Euis Soliha, Fadillah Ega, Firmansyah, Grace, Grecia, Gusti, Habibburahman, Handayani, Hendri, Hujimatul Fauziah, I Putu Dony, I wayan Agus Permana, Indrayana, Jantje, Jermias, Jhonly, Josiah, Kurniasari, Lestari, Maartje, Mananeke, Manto, Marzuki Noor, Masrifani, Meirilin, Michael Tactria, Mohdari, Mocica Fradisha Zukhri, Rusnaeni, Nekko, Novi, Nugroho, Nursanti Sem Christina Hawila, Octovian, Okka Raisa, Olivia Mimin, Paais, Permana Diamond Komala, Pio William Augustine, R A J Sri Wulandari, Randy Richi, Rani, Rebecca, Retno Tri, Reza, Richard Andre, Rizki Amalia, Rukhviyanti, Sahanggamu Lisbeth, Saiyang, Sari, Sarinah, Sefti Riana, Sembiring, Sepang, Septian Hardhanto, Sibagaring, Siregar, Slamet Ario Susanto, Sri Rejeki, Stefhanie, Suparwa, Susena, Sutanti, Suwandi, Suwarni, Karona Cahya, Suwarni, Syaifuddin Fahmi, Tanan, Tangkilisan, Tiara, Tinjung Desy, Todi Rahmat, Unti Ludigdo, Utomo Deni, Vulandari, Wahyu, Waleleng Frentino, Widi Dewi Ruspitasari, Wijayanti, Wika, William Agustin, Yunus Handoko, Yunus

1

Source: Data processed, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Sharia and Conventional Bank Sinarmas

There are several things that need to be considered in knowing bibliometric results with VOSviewer software, namely: first, the software interface, namely the VOSviewer interface displays diagrams and graphs that visualize publication data. Users can open and explore these charts and graphs by clicking on specific items or zooming in on specific parts of the diagram. Second, visual components, namely several visual components that may appear in VOSviewer bibliometric results including nodes (representations of publications), lines (representations of connection citation), And color (representation from category or topic). Third, citation network analysis, namely citation network analysis helps in determining relationships between publications and understanding how publications are related to each other. Larger nodes in the diagram represent more widely noted publications and relationships between nodes can help in understanding how publications are related. Fourth, cluster analysis, namely cluster analysis helps in determining relationships between topics or fields of science and understanding how publications are related to topics or fields knowledge certain. Color in diagram represent category or topic And helps in understanding how publications relate to different topics or fields of science. Fifth, citation analysis, namely citation analysis helps in determining the most noted publications and understanding how publications are related to each other. Larger nodes in the diagram represent more publications

noted and helps in understanding how publications relate to each other. The results are as follows:

Picture 1. Visualization networks map development study around Bank Sinarmas Sharia and Conventional

Source: Data processed, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Co-word map network visualization of research developments regarding Bank Sinarmas Syariah and Conventional are divided into 9 clusters and 94 topics, as follows:

- Cluster 1. Color red, consists from 16 topic, that is: bank Sinarmas, brands image, banking sector, brand image, brand loyalty, brand trust, company, competition, consumer loyalty, customer value, experiential marketing, population, product, profitability, regression equation, sample, service.
- Cluster 2. Color green, consists from 14 topic, that is: analysis, communication, conflict management, customer, customer loyalty, customer trust, influence, loyalty, relationship marketing variable, sampling technique, significance value, significant influence, trust, value.
- Cluster 3. Blue, consisting of 12 topics, namely: compensation, discipline, employee, employee job satisfaction, employee performance, job satisfaction, performance, recruitment, reward, significant effect, situational leadership style, training.
- Cluster 4. Color yellow, consists from 12 topic, that is: assets, bank Sinarmas Kupang branch, capital, capital adequacyratio, car, eps, equity, financial statement, pt bank Sinarmas tbk, return, roa, roe.
- Cluster 5. Purple, consisting of 12 topics, namely: customer satisfaction, e banking, effect, efficiency, PT Bank Sinarmas KCP A Yani Banjarmasin, quality, reliability, respondent, responsiveness, service quality, service quality, validity.
- Cluster 6. Light blue, consists of 11 topics, namely: bank, branch, collateral appraisal, credits, debtor, difference, effort, loans, observation, Sinarmas bank, third party funds.

- Cluster 7. Orange, consists of 8 topics, namely: amount, bulletin, hypothesis, office stationery, improving employee performance, PT Bank Sinarmas Cliff Tinggi Jambi, relationships, Sinarmas Bank employees.
- Cluster 8. Brown color, consists of 5 topics, namely: competence, direct effect, employee empowerment, employee work performance, questionnaire.
- Cluster 9. Light purple, consists of 4 topics, namely: bank Sinarmas Ambon, employee performance, significant to, significant to employee performance.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research Regarding Problems at Bank Sinarmas Syariah and Conventional

Based on study studies Library Research on journals study Which has been downloaded, there are 2 problems with Bank Sinarmas (Budianto, 2023) (Dewi et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023), namely:

First, agreement credit For prevent credit problematic. For To prevent problematic credit at Bank Sinarmas, a strict and careful credit agreement must be made to ensure that the borrower meets all the requirements and criteria set by the bank before being approved to receive credit. Here are some things to consider in a credit agreement:

- (1) Credit Analysis: Bank Sinarmas must carry out a careful credit analysis of the borrower to ensure that the borrower has the financial capacity and eligibility to repay the credit with the specified interest and time period.
- (2) Condition Guarantee: Bank Sinarmas must request guarantee or guarantee adequate from borrower For ensure that bank own asset Which can be taken If borrower fail pay return credit. Type guarantee Which may be requested including securities, property, or motor vehicles.
- (3) Provision Payment: Agreement credit must load provision the payment clear And detailed Which determine amount payment principal And interest that the borrower must pay on each maturity date.
- (4) Sanctions: The credit agreement must include sanctions that will be imposed on the borrower if he fails to repay the credit at the specified time. This sanction can be in the form of fines or higher interest that will be charged on the unpaid credit amount.
- (5) Supervision: Bank Sinarmas must supervise the credit provided to ensure that borrowers meet all the requirements and criteria set out in the credit agreement. Banks must also monitor borrowers' financial performance to ensure that they are able to repay credit smoothly.

With make agreement credit Which strict And careful, Bank Sinarmas can reduce the risk of problematic credit and ensure that the credit provided is guaranteed and safe.

Second, terminating MSME credit using the Internal Control System/SPI, which can be done in the following way:

- (1) Risk Identification: First of all, the bank or financial institution needs to identify the risks associated with terminating MSME credit. These risks can include credit risk, liquidity risk, market risk and operational risk.
- (2) Evaluation Risk: After risk identified, bank or institution finance must assess these risks. Risk assessment must be carried out systematically and structured For ensure that risk Which related with termination MSME credit is properly identified and managed effectively.
- (3) Policy and Procedure Development: Once risks are assessed, the bank

or institution finance must develop policy And procedure Which appropriate to manage these risks. These policies and procedures should cover aspects such as data and information collection, credit worthiness assessment, credit management, and credit monitoring.

- (4) Implementation of Policies and Procedures: Once policies and procedures are developed, the bank or financial institution must implement those policies and procedures. This includes implementing procedures and controls.
- (5) Monitoring and Evaluation: Once policies and procedures are implemented, the bank or institution finance must monitor And evaluate performance internal control system to ensure that MSME credit provided is taken with measurable risks.

In all This process is important for bank or institution finance to ensure that the internal control process is designed and implemented correctly and continues to be improved in order to reduce risks and ensure the success of MSME credit termination.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research About Determinant Performance Finance Bank Sinarmas Sharia and Conventional

Based on study studies Library Research on journals study Which has been downloaded, there is 5 determinant performance finance Bank Sinarmas (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rohimah et al., 2023), namely:

First, determine the capital ratio/Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR through Return On Assets/ROA and Return On Equity/ROE. The influence of ROA and ROE on capital ratios can vary depending on the financial and operational conditions of a company. In general, the higher the ROA and ROE of a company, the lower the capital ratio. This is because high ROA and ROE indicate that the company is able to generate greater profits from asset or equity Which he has, so that need capital Which less to support its operational activities. However, the influence of ROA and ROE on capital ratios can also depend on the industry or sector in which the company is located operate, as well as strategy business Which applied by company the. There are several examples where companies with high ROA and ROE also have ratio capital Which tall, like company technology Which requires capital Which big For do study And development product new. In this case, it is important to carry out a more in-depth analysis of financial performance And operational something company For determine connection between ROA, ROE, And ratio capital. Analysis This can help investors And analyst finance in understanding the financial condition of a company and the potential investment profits that can be generated.

Second, the growth of Third Party Funds/DPK. In June 2021, Bank Sinarmas' DPK reached IDR 97.6 trillion, an increase of 7.5% compared to the same period the previous year. Of the total DPK, current and savings deposits experienced growth of 12.7% and 14.6% respectively compared to the same period the previous year. This good growth in deposits is supported by Bank Sinarmas' strategy in improving banking services and products Which innovative, as well as expand network branch And network ATM in throughout Indonesia.

Third, determinant health bank through Non Performing Loans/NPLs, Interest Rate Risk Ratio/IRR, Loans to Deposits Ratio/LDR, Loans to Assets Ratio/LAR, Cash Ratio, Good Corporate Governance/GCG, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Net Interest Margin/NIM, Operating

Expenses to Operating Income/BOPO, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR. The explanation is:

- Non-Performing Loans (NPL): NPL is the ratio of overdue loans during more from 90 day with total credit Which owned bank. If NPL levels are high, this shows that the bank is experiencing internal problems managing credit risk, and the likelihood of incurring losses. Therefore, the lower the NPL level, the healthier Bank Sinarmas' financial performance.
- Interest Rate Risk Ratio (IRR): IRR is ratio Which show the bank's ability to deal with changes in interest rates. If the IRR is too high, the bank may face high risks if interest rates rise. Conversely, if IRR too low, bank Possible No capable produce income sufficient. Therefore, the more balanced Bank Sinarmas' IRR is, the healthier its performance.
- Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR): LDR is a ratio that shows how much a bank loan is compared to the deposits received. If the LDR is too high, the bank may face liquidity risks, as it may not have enough funds to repay the loan if necessary. Conversely, if the LDR is too low, the bank may not be able to maximize its earnings potential. Therefore, the more balanced Bank Sinarmas' LDR is, the healthier its performance.
- Loan to Asset Ratio (LAR): LAR is the ratio between a bank's loans and its total assets. The higher the LAR, the greater the risk of the bank experiencing bankruptcy If happen fail pay loan. By Because That, the more The lower Bank Sinarmas' LAR, the healthier its performance.
- Cash Ratio: Cash ratio shows the bank's ability to fulfill its obligations financial period short with cash or asset liquid other. The higher the cash ratio, the easier it is for the bank to fulfill its financial obligations and the healthier its performance.
- Good Corporate Governance (GCG): GCG includes good corporate governance, including appropriate risk management, transparency, and accountability. If Bank Sinarmas has strong GCG practices, it will reduce the risk of failure in managing operational, reputation and regulatory risks, resulting in healthier performance.
- Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE: The higher the ROA and ROE values, the more Good performance finance bank. This show that bank able to produce profit Which tall from asset Which he has And provide high profits to shareholders. However, too high ROA and ROE levels can also indicate higher risk, such as taking greater risks in investments.
- Net Interest Margin/NIM: NIM Also is indicator important health bank. The more tall mark NIM, the more big ability bank in generate income flower. However, mark NIM Which too tall Also can indicates higher risk, such as higher credit risk or operational risk.
- Operational Expenses to Operating Income/BOPO: The higher the BOPO, the lower the bank's efficiency in managing its operational costs, so that it can affect the health level of Bank Sinarmas. If Bank Sinarmas BOPO high, p This can signify that the operational costs incurred by the bank are greater than the income earned, so it can have an impact negative to profitability bank. Besides That, BOPO Which tall It can also indicate inefficiency in managing operational costs, so that efforts are needed to reduce operational expenses so that BOPO is lower. In the long term, high BOPO can reduce Bank Sinarmas' financial performance, such as reducing ROA (Return On Assets) And ROE (Return On Equity), which can have an impact on decline trust

customers And investors to bank.

- Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR). CAR is ratio Which measure comparison between capital bank with risk Which faced by bank, especially risk credit. A high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient capital to cover its credit risks. Conversely, a low CAR indicates that the bank may not have sufficient capital to cover risk credit And can experience difficulty finance. For Bank Sinarmas, CAR is one of the main indicators that can influence the bank's financial health. As a bank that focuses on financing and credit, CAR Which tall can help Bank Sinarmas to minimize the credit risks it faces. Therefore, the higher CAR Bank Sinarmas, the more Healthy also condition finance bank the.
- Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR). FDR is a ratio that measures the comparison between the amount of financing provided by the bank and the amount of funds collected from customers through deposits. A high FDR indicates that there are more banks provide financing compared to the amount of funds collected from customers. This may indicate a risk liquidity Which more tall Because bank Possible difficulty For fulfill customer fund withdrawal requests. For Bank Sinarmas, a healthy FDR is a low FDR, because this shows that the bank is able to manage funds received from customers well and obtain sources funding Which Enough For finance activity its operations. A low FDR can also indicate that Bank Sinarmas is more careful in its operations give financing so that can minimize risk credit that he has.

Fourth, determine share price fluctuations through Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Earning Per Share/EPS. The explanation is:

- Return On Assets (ROA). ROA measures a company's ability to produce profit from every amount asset Which he has. The more tall ROA, increasingly efficient company in manage his assets For produce profit. This can affect share prices because investors tend to look for companies that have high and consistent ROA.
- Return On Equity (ROE). ROE measure ability something company in generating profits from each amount of equity it owns. The higher the ROE, the more big profit resulting from by company for each amount of capital invested by the owner or investor. This can affect share prices because investors tend to look for companies that have a high and consistent ROE.
- Earnings Per Share (EPS). EPS measures the net profit generated by a company for each share outstanding. The higher the EPS, the more big profit Which generated by company For every shares owned by investors. This can affect share prices because investors tend to look for companies that have high and consistent EPS.

Fifth, determinant profitability through credit problematic And cash turnover.

The explanation is as following:

- Problem Loans (Non Performing Loans/NPL). NPLs can have a negative impact on profitability bank Because can cause decline income and improvement cost operational. When credit problematic increase, bank have to set aside reserve For cover risk credit Which Possible happen And If the bank is unable to resolve problem loans, then the bank must bear the losses from the credit. Problematic credit can affect profitability bank through two method that is, First with reducing interest income and secondly by increasing operational costs. When

problem loans increase, banks have to incur costs to resolve the problem, such as collection costs credit, cost law and cost other which are related with handling problem loans.

- Cash Turnover (Cash Turnover). Cash turnover can affect bank profitability because good cash turnover can increase income bank. Rotation cash Which Good can achieved by increasing giving credit And interesting fund from customers. The more The higher the cash turnover, the more likely the bank is to generate greater income. However, cash turnover that is too high can also have a negative impact on bank profitability because the bank may have to pay higher interest to attract funds from customers and greater operational costs to process credit grants more quickly.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research About Innovation Which Done Bank Sinarmas Sharia and Conventional

Based on study studies Library Research on journals study Which has been downloaded, there is 2 innovation Which done Bank Sinarmas (Budianto & Goddess, 2023) (Rohmandika et al., 2023), namely:

First, information system applications. Bank Sinarmas has various system applications information Which used For support operational business And provide better service to customers. Some examples of information system applications used at Bank Sinarmas include: (1) Core Banking System, namely this application is used to manage daily banking transactions, such as opening accounts, depositing and withdrawing funds, transferring between accounts, and paying bills; (2) Internet Banking, that is application This possible customers For carry out banking transactions via the internet, such as transferring funds, paying bills, purchasing credit, and opening deposits; (3) Mobile Banking, namely this application allows customers to carry out banking transactions via mobile devices, such as smartphones or tablets; (4) ATM, namely this application allows customers to carry out banking transactions, such as withdrawing funds, transferring between accounts, payment bill, And purchase credit, through machine ATM; (5) Customer Relationships Management (CRM), that is application This used For manage customer information, such as customer profiles, transaction history and service preferences; (6) Risk Management System, that is application This used For monitor risk business, such as risk credit, risk operational, And risk market; And (7) Business Intelligence (BI), namely the application This used For analyze data transaction And behavior customer, so that it can give information Which useful For develop product And better service.

Second, the application for calculating customer points. The application for calculating customer points at Bank Sinarmas is based on a loyalty program called Sinar Reward. Program This possible customers Bank Sinarmas For gather points by making certain transactions with their credit or debit cards, and then exchanging these points for various prizes such as electronic goods, plane tickets, or discount shopping in shops certain. For gather points, Customers must make transactions with a Bank Sinarmas credit or debit card. Each transaction made will provide different points depending on the type of transaction and nominal purchase. The larger the nominal purchase, the more points the customer will get. To find out the number of points you have collected, customers can see it in report transaction card credit or their discharge. Apart from that, customers can also see the number of points available and options

prizes that can be exchanged through the Sinar Reward service on the Bank Sinarmas website or mobile application. Once customers collect enough points, they can exchange it with present Which available in program Ray Rewards. Customers can choose present Which desired from catalog present Which available And exchange points via the Sinar Reward service on the Bank Sinarmas website or mobile application.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research About Determinant Performance Employee Bank Sinarmas Sharia and Conventional

Based on study studies Library Research on journals study Which has been downloaded, there is 13 determinant performance employee Bank Sinarmas (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023), namely:

First, the company's internal media relations. The company's internal media can influence employee performance and overall company productivity. A strong relationship between employees and the company can help build self-confidence, motivation and high job satisfaction in employees. Internal company media, such as newspapers or newsletters company, employee portal, or employee meeting, can be used to strengthen these relationships by providing transparent and clear information about the company's direction, goals, and values, as well as give opportunities for employees to provide input and feedback.

Second, the relationship between Work Life Balance and Employee Engagement. Work life balance is a balance between an employee's work life and personal life. Employees who have a good work life balance tend to have higher job satisfaction and are likely to be more engaged in their work, which in turn can increase their employee engagement. Employee engagement can improve employee performance and company productivity significantly whole. Company can help in facilitate work life balance for its employees by providing employee welfare programs, flexibility in working hours, and support in stress management.

Third, competency empowerment. Competency empowerment can improve employee performance by providing them with the skills and knowledge needed to complete tasks effectively and efficiently. In the context of Bank Sinarmas, increasing employee competency can help improve service quality and customer experience, as well as increase efficiency and effectiveness in business processes. Companies can provide training and development to employees to strengthen their competencies, which in turn can improve employee performance and customer satisfaction.

Fourth, recruitment. Good recruitment can ensure that Bank Sinarmas gets quality employees who suit the organization's needs. Process recruitment that can be effective produce employees who have the right skills, knowledge and abilities to meet job requirements. Employee Which recruited with Good Also can bring experience and new perspectives into the organization, which can enrich teamwork dynamics and innovation.

Fifth, position promotion. Job promotions can motivate employees to improve their performance, because promotions are considered a form of recognition good performance. Promotion position can also improve self-confidence and motivation employees, because they are feel valued by organization And see that there are opportunities for growth in the company. By increasing employee motivation and self-confidence, their performance can improve.

Sixth, training. Training can help Bank Sinarmas employees to develop Skills And knowledge they in field work

they. Training can help employees understand the latest changes in technology, procedures and industry requirements that may affect their performance. Employees who continue to develop through training can help improve the quality and efficiency of their work, thereby improving their performance.

Seventh, discipline. Good discipline can improve employee performance by keeping them working according to established rules and procedures. Discipline too help improve quality work And productivity. If employees are not disciplined, they tend to disobey regulations, complete work poorly, and experience decreased productivity.

Eighth, awards. Providing appropriate and consistent rewards can increase employee motivation to work harder and improve their performance. Rewards also help increase employee job satisfaction and give flavor valued And acknowledged on Work hard they. If If employees do not receive proper recognition, they tend to lose motivation and trust in their company, which can affect their performance negatively.

Ninth, situational leadership style. Situational leadership style plays role important in increase performance employee. Style leadership that appropriate can increase motivation, involvement, And trust employee to their leaders, which can influence their performance positively. The right situational leadership style can also help employees to develop their abilities and skills, which can improve their overall performance.

Tenth, compensation. Good compensation can motivate employees to work better and increase productivity. Employees who feel valued and appreciated for the work they do tend to be more motivated to work hard and produce better results.

Eleventh, individual workload. Individual workload that is too heavy can have a negative impact on employee performance. Employees who feel too tired or overwhelmed with work tend to be less productive and effective.

Twelfth, organizational workload. Organizational workloads that are too high can also be negative impact on employee performance. If employees feel that their tasks and responsibilities are too many and too difficult to handle, then this can cause stress and fatigue which ultimately affects their performance. By Because That, Bank Sinarmas need ensure that burden organizational work is not too high and in accordance with capacity and employee abilities. Third mercy, bonus annual. Bonus annual can become incentive for employees For Work with more Good And increase performance they. Employees who know that they will receive a bonus if they achieve certain targets or Work with Good tend more motivated For Work hard And give results Which more Good.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research Regarding Determinants of Customer Interest and Satisfaction in Saving at Bank Sinarmas Syariah and Conventional

Based on study studies Library Research on journals study Which has been downloaded, there are 9 determinants of customer interest and satisfaction in saving at Bank Sinarmas, namely:

First, service quality. Good service quality can help increase customer satisfaction and build a more positive relationship between customers and the bank. Customers who are satisfied with bank services tend to be more loyal and may recommend the bank to others. Therefore, improving service quality can help increase customer loyalty.

Second, E-Banking. E-banking allows customers to carry out transactions easily and comfortably via the internet. With increasing development technology And style life Which the more Busy, e-banking can is an important factor in maintaining loyal customers. Customers who use e-banking regularly and find the platform easy to use can increase customer satisfaction and loyalty to the bank.

Third, trust. Trust is a key factor in forming relationships Which good between customers And bank. Customer must feel believe that the bank will maintain the security and confidentiality of their information, provide good service, and resolve problems quickly and effectively. If customers feel his trust maintained, they more tend For still loyal with the bank and maintain long-term relationships.

Fourth, Mobile Banking. In the digital era, Mobile Banking is an important factor in maintaining customer loyalty. Mobile Banking enables customers For access service banking from where just And When just, so give convenience And comfort for customers in transaction. Besides Therefore, the features offered by Mobile Banking such as bill payments, fund transfers and purchasing banking products can make customers even more attached to Bank Sinarmas.

Fifth, Customer Relationship Marketing/CRM. Customer Relationship Marketing (CRM) is a strategic approach in building long-term relationships with customers. CRM helps Bank Sinarmas understand customer needs and desires, so that it can provide more personalized service and in accordance with customer needs. With more personalized service, customers will feel appreciated and increasingly connected to Bank Sinarmas.

Sixth, Customers Value. Customers Value is mark Which given by Sinarmas Bank to customers in the form of satisfactory service and prices competitive. The greater the value provided by Bank Sinarmas to customers, the higher the customer loyalty to Bank Sinarmas. Therefore, Bank Sinarmas must ensure that the products and services offered are of good quality and provide clear benefits for customers.

Seventh, service electronics/E-Servqual. Study show that Good electronic service will increase customer satisfaction and in turn will increase customer loyalty. E-Servqual consists of several dimensions such as reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and physical evidence. The better the quality of the E-Servqual service provided by Bank Sinarmas, the higher the customer loyalty.

Eighth, price. Price also has a significant influence on customer loyalty. Customer tend still loyal on Bank Sinarmas If price Which provided affordable and in accordance with the value they receive. However, if the price given is too high, customers can switch to another bank that offers more competitive prices.

Ninth, image company. Image company Also influence loyalty customers. Customer will tend still loyal on Bank Sinarmas If image company looks good in the eyes of customers. Company image can be measured from several dimensions such as trust, quality and credibility. The better the company image, the higher customer loyalty.

Conclusion

Based on results discussion on, can concluded as following:

First, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding Bank Sinarmas Sharia And Conventional during period time year 2010 until year 2023 which comes from the journal nationally accredited by

Sinta, there are 50 articles publication journal. Journal Administration Public And Journal EMBA: Journal Research Economy, Management, Business and Accounting are the journal publishing institutions that publish the most research results on Bank Sinarmas Syariah and Conventional. Areros, Dwi Budi, Putra, Srisulistiowati, and Trisnowati are the most productive researchers writing about Bank Sinarmas Syariah and Conventional.

Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, network visualization results around Bank Sinarmas Sharia And Conventional divided become 9 cluster and 94 items topic. Cluster 1 consists from 16 topic, cluster 2 consists from 14 topic, cluster 3 consists from 12 topic, cluster 4 consists from 12 topics, cluster 5 consists from 12 topic, cluster 6 consists from 11 topic, cluster 7 consists from 8 topic, cluster 8 consists from 5 topic, And cluster 9 consists from 4 topics.

Third, based on the mapping of the Library Research study, there are 5 topics related to Bank Sinarmas Syariah and Conventional, namely: (1) Problems in Bank Sinarmas; (2) Determinant performance finance Bank Sinarmas; (3) Innovation carried out by Bank Sinarmas; (4) Determining the performance of Bank Sinarmas employees; and (5) Determinants of customer interest and satisfaction in transactions at Bank Sinarmas.

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